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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE INVISIBLE LOAD”

Quietly, carrying it
The weight of shame
Following me around
Which I, myself is to blame

The burden that bent every moment
Which sometimes is too much to bear
Making every track dark
How I wish I could share

Some days I am down
Some days up
But slowly through silence
Emotions start to erupt

And now, when sadness visits
I say, come in
But I do not show it
Like it's part of my skin